

Table 1. Multiseason correlated-replicate model selection results for probability of detection for eastern wild turkeys at stations along gobbling call-count survey routes in southeast Wisconsin, USA, 2016–2018. Models were ranked by the difference (ΔAIC_c) between the model with the lowest Akaike’s Information Criterion for small samples (AIC_c) and AIC_c for the current model, K is the number of model parameters, w_i is model weight, and $-2\log(L)$ is the maximized -2 log-likelihood function. Model fit was assessed in Program PRESENCE v12.23 (Hines 2006).

Probability of detection model ^a	K	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	w_i	$-2\log(L)$
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time}^2 + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$ ^b	21	3,405.26	0.00	0.859	3,351.85
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time}^2 + \text{Wind} + (\text{Time} \times \text{Wind})\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,408.93	3.67	0.137	3,342.04
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time} + \text{Wind} + (\text{Time} \times \text{Wind})\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	21	3,417.68	12.42	0.002	3,364.27
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time}^2\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	17	3,417.85	12.59	0.002	3,376.65
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time} + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	17	3,420.31	15.05	0.000	3,379.11
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	13	3,423.43	18.17	0.000	3,393.34
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date} + \text{Time} + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	21	3,426.58	21.32	0.000	3,373.17
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Time}^2\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,428.69	23.43	0.000	3,361.81
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	13	3,435.10	29.84	0.000	3,405.01
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Time} + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,435.79	30.53	0.000	3,368.91
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	21	3,439.17	33.91	0.000	3,385.76
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time} + \text{Wind} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,440.73	35.47	0.000	3,373.85
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date} + \text{Time} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,446.35	41.09	0.000	3,379.47
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Time} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,451.70	46.44	0.000	3,369.86
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Wind} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	21	3,451.71	46.45	0.000	3,398.30
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Noise}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	13	3,455.73	50.47	0.000	3,425.64
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	9	3,456.30	51.04	0.000	3,436.36
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date} + \text{Wind} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,458.50	53.24	0.000	3,391.62
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	13	3,458.80	53.54	0.000	3,428.71
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Precip}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	13	3,460.84	55.58	0.000	3,430.75
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Temp}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	13	3,461.56	56.30	0.000	3,431.47
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	17	3,462.64	57.38	0.000	3,421.44
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	17	3,464.72	59.46	0.000	3,423.52
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	21	3,468.62	63.36	0.000	3,415.22
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\cdot\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	6	3,469.91	64.65	0.000	3,457.04
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Wind} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,470.67	65.41	0.000	3,388.83
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Year}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	8	3,471.38	66.12	0.000	3,453.85
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\cdot\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{Season}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	17	3,472.19	66.93	0.000	3,430.99

Table 1: detection model set

$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\{.\}$	25	3,477.82	72.56	0.000	3,410.94
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Full}\}, \pi\{.\}$	41	3,527.37	122.11	0.000	3,388.91

^a Model parameters include route occupancy (ψ), local availability at a survey station given unavailability at the previous station (θ), local availability at a survey station given availability at the previous station (θ'), establishment (γ), abandonment (ε), detection (p), and availability at the unobserved survey station defined by the Markov equilibrium process via θ and θ' (π). All parameters besides detection probability were held constant (.) to evaluate the potential influence of environmental covariate(s) on gobbling activity and the ability of observers to detect wild turkeys. Continuous detection covariates were standardized and include time of day (Time), time in quadratic form (Time²), Julian date (Date), Julian date in quadratic form (Date²), average wind speed (Wind), and temperature (Temp). Categorical covariates include annual survey period (Survey Period), study season (Season), study year (Year), sky conditions (Sky; cloudy, partly cloudy, or clear), whether precipitation occurred during the survey (Precip), whether there was a noise disturbance during the survey (Noise), surveyor that conducted the survey (Observer), and a full identity model where detection is different on each survey (Full).

^b Top-supported model ($\Delta\text{AIC}_c < 2$) within the southeast Wisconsin detection model set which was further used as the base model in the subsequent model set to evaluate local availability of wild turkeys (Table 2).

Table 2. Multiseason correlated-replicate model selection results for probability of local availability for eastern wild turkeys within 1.6-km buffered (813.7 ha) stations along gobbling call-count surveys routes in southeast Wisconsin, USA, 2016–2018. Models were ranked by the difference (ΔAIC_c) between the model with the lowest Akaike’s Information Criterion for small samples (AIC_c) and AIC_c for the current model, K is the number of model parameters, w_i is model weight, and $-2\log(L)$ is the maximized -2 log-likelihood function. Model fit was assessed in Program PRESENCE v12.23 (Hines 2006).

Probability of local availability model ^a	K	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	w_i	$-2\log(L)$
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{hard}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}^b, \pi\{\cdot\}^c$	27	3,348.33	0.00	0.701	3,274.17
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{hard}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{hard}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,352.70	4.38	0.079	3,270.87
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,353.97	5.64	0.042	3,287.09
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{hard}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{hard}} + \text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,354.89	6.56	0.026	3,273.05
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,355.09	6.77	0.024	3,288.21
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,355.90	7.57	0.016	3,289.02
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,356.13	7.80	0.014	3,289.25
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	23	3,356.25	7.92	0.013	3,296.28
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	27	3,356.63	8.30	0.011	3,282.47
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,356.85	8.52	0.010	3,289.96
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	23	3,356.91	8.58	0.010	3,296.94
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,357.82	9.50	0.006	3,290.94
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,357.94	9.61	0.006	3,291.06
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	27	3,358.20	9.87	0.005	3,284.04
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,358.60	10.27	0.004	3,291.71
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CONTAG}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	23	3,358.80	10.47	0.004	3,298.82
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,358.91	10.58	0.004	3,292.02
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,359.03	10.70	0.003	3,292.15
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{IJI}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,359.30	10.97	0.003	3,292.42
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,359.83	11.50	0.002	3,292.95
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,359.93	11.60	0.002	3,293.05
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,360.01	11.69	0.002	3,293.13
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	27	3,360.41	12.08	0.002	3,286.25
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,360.71	12.38	0.001	3,293.83
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	23	3,360.82	12.50	0.001	3,300.85
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	25	3,361.16	12.84	0.001	3,294.28
$\psi\{\cdot\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	23	3,361.78	13.45	0.001	3,301.81

Table 2: local availability model set

$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,361.86	13.53	0.001	3,294.97
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,362.09	13.76	0.001	3,295.20
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}} + \text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,362.20	13.87	0.001	3,295.32
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,362.39	14.07	0.001	3,288.23
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,362.47	14.15	0.001	3,295.59
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,362.53	14.20	0.001	3,288.37
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,362.55	14.23	0.001	3,295.67
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{IJI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,363.35	15.02	0.000	3,289.19
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{IJI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,363.79	15.46	0.000	3,289.63
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,364.25	15.92	0.000	3,304.27
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,364.62	16.29	0.000	3,290.46
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,364.64	16.31	0.000	3,290.48
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{ENN}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,364.91	16.58	0.000	3,290.75
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,365.14	16.81	0.000	3,298.25
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,365.43	17.10	0.000	3,298.54
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,365.56	17.23	0.000	3,291.40
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,365.69	17.36	0.000	3,291.53
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,365.89	17.56	0.000	3,291.73
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,366.02	17.70	0.000	3,291.86
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,366.11	17.78	0.000	3,291.95
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,366.65	18.32	0.000	3,299.77
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,367.27	18.94	0.000	3,293.11
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{EDGE}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,367.40	19.08	0.000	3,307.43
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,367.69	19.37	0.000	3,293.53
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,368.37	20.04	0.000	3,308.40
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,369.38	21.05	0.000	3,309.40
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,369.79	21.47	0.000	3,309.82
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,370.19	21.87	0.000	3,296.03
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,370.36	22.04	0.000	3,303.48
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,371.53	23.20	0.000	3,297.37
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,371.84	23.52	0.000	3,311.87
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,371.88	23.55	0.000	3,311.91
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,371.91	23.58	0.000	3,297.75
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,372.46	24.13	0.000	3,290.62

Table 2: local availability model set

$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,372.51	24.18	0.000	3,298.35
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,373.32	24.99	0.000	3,291.49
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,373.33	25.00	0.000	3,299.17
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,373.86	25.53	0.000	3,306.97
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,374.25	25.92	0.000	3,300.09
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,374.59	26.26	0.000	3,292.75
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{CWED}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,375.23	26.91	0.000	3,301.07
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,375.85	27.52	0.000	3,315.88
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,376.05	27.72	0.000	3,309.17
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,376.53	28.20	0.000	3,316.55
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,376.53	28.20	0.000	3,302.37
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,376.98	28.65	0.000	3,302.82
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{IJ}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,377.21	28.88	0.000	3,317.23
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,378.15	29.82	0.000	3,318.17
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,380.94	32.61	0.000	3,314.05
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,381.40	33.07	0.000	3,321.43
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,382.01	33.68	0.000	3,322.03
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,382.55	34.22	0.000	3,322.58
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{IJ}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,383.15	34.82	0.000	3,323.17
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,383.48	35.15	0.000	3,309.32
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,383.69	35.36	0.000	3,323.72
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,385.50	37.17	0.000	3,318.61
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,391.02	42.69	0.000	3,331.05
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,391.94	43.62	0.000	3,331.97
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,395.30	46.97	0.000	3,335.32
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,396.34	48.01	0.000	3,336.36
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,397.04	48.71	0.000	3,337.06
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,399.78	51.45	0.000	3,339.80
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,400.55	52.22	0.000	3,340.57
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,400.91	52.59	0.000	3,340.94
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,401.06	52.73	0.000	3,341.09
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	23	3,401.37	53.05	0.000	3,341.40
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,401.47	53.15	0.000	3,334.59
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	25	3,401.80	53.47	0.000	3,334.92

Table 2: local availability model set

$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{AREA_{dec}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	25	3,403.50	55.17	0.000	3,336.61
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{AREA_{grass}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	25	3,403.55	55.22	0.000	3,336.67
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{PLAND_{oak}^2 + PROX_{ag}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	27	3,404.88	56.55	0.000	3,330.72
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}^d$	21	3,405.26	56.93	0.000	3,351.85
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{PLAND_{oak}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	23	3,410.36	62.03	0.000	3,350.38
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{CLUMPY_{oak}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	23	3,410.39	62.06	0.000	3,350.41
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{LPI_{oak}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	23	3,410.84	62.51	0.000	3,350.86
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{AREA_{oak}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	23	3,411.41	63.08	0.000	3,351.44
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{PROX_{oak}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	23	3,411.44	63.12	0.000	3,351.47
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{AREA_{oak}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	25	3,411.85	63.52	0.000	3,344.97
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{STRATA\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,414.00	65.67	0.000	3,332.17
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{PLAND_{oak}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	25	3,416.34	68.01	0.000	3,349.45
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{LPI_{oak}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{best_{se}\}, \pi\{.\}$	25	3,417.34	69.01	0.000	3,350.46

^a Model parameters include route occupancy (ψ), local availability at a survey station given unavailability at the previous station (θ), local availability at a survey station given availability at the previous station (θ'), establishment (γ), abandonment (ε), detection (p), and availability at the unobserved survey station defined by the Markov equilibrium process via θ and θ' (π). Occupancy, establishment, and abandonment parameters were held constant (.) to evaluate the potential influence of land cover covariate(s) on probability of local availability (θ and θ') of wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin. Covariates include class-level composition and configuration metrics (McGarigal et al. 2012) for agriculture (ag), deciduous forest (dec), forest cover (forest), herbaceous-grassland (grass), upland hardwoods (hard), oak forest (oak), and open cover (open): area-weighted mean patch size (AREA), clumpiness index (CLUMPY), area-weighted mean Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (ENN), interspersion and juxtaposition index (IJI), largest patch index (LPI), percentage of land cover (PLAND), and mean proximity index (PROX). We also assessed forest cover strata (STRATA; $\leq 20\%$ forest, >20 to $\leq 40\%$ forest, >40 to $\leq 60\%$ forest, >60 to $\leq 80\%$ forest, and $>80\%$ forest) and the following landscape configuration metrics (McGarigal et al. 2012): edge density (EDGE), contrast-weighted edge density (CWED), IJI, and contagion index (CONTAG).

^b Detection probability covariates ($p\{best_{se}\}$) from the best-supported model for wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (Survey Period, Time², Wind; Table 1).

^c Top-supported model ($\Delta AIC_c < 2$) within the local availability model set which was further used as the base models in the subsequent model set to evaluate route occupancy of wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (Table 3).

^d Best-supported detection probability (p) model for wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (Table 1).

Table 3. Multiseason correlated-replicate model selection results for probability of route occupancy for eastern wild turkeys within 3.2-km buffered (~5,300 ha) gobbling call-count survey routes in southeast Wisconsin, USA, 2016–2018. Models were ranked by the difference (ΔAIC_c) between the model with the lowest Akaike’s Information Criterion for small samples (AIC_c) and AIC_c for the current model, K is the number of model parameters, w_i is model weight, and $-2\log(L)$ is the maximized -2 log-likelihood function. Model fit was assessed in Program PRESENCE v12.23 (Hines 2006). Non-converging models are not included within the model set.

Probability of route occupancy model ^a	K	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	w_i	$-2\log(L)$
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}^b, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}^c, \pi\}^d$	28	3,336.60	0.00	0.654	3,258.66
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	28	3,338.72	2.11	0.227	3,260.77
$\psi\{\text{EDGE}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	28	3,345.76	9.15	0.007	3,267.81
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	28	3,346.21	9.61	0.005	3,268.26
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	28	3,346.60	10.00	0.004	3,268.66
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	28	3,347.00	10.39	0.004	3,269.05
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.14	10.53	0.003	3,265.30
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{dec}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.47	10.87	0.003	3,265.63
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	28	3,347.48	10.87	0.003	3,269.53
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{dec}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.58	10.97	0.003	3,265.74
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.72	11.12	0.003	3,265.89
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.86	11.26	0.002	3,266.03
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.91	11.31	0.002	3,266.08
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}} + \text{EDGE}_{\text{ag}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.92	11.32	0.002	3,266.08
$\psi\{\text{EDGE}_{\text{dec}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	28	3,347.99	11.39	0.002	3,270.05
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{oak}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	28	3,348.15	11.55	0.002	3,270.21
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{dec}} + \text{EDGE}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.16	11.56	0.002	3,266.33
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.19	11.58	0.002	3,266.35
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.20	11.59	0.002	3,266.36
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}} + \text{EDGE}_{\text{dec}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.23	11.63	0.002	3,266.40
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{ag}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.23	11.63	0.002	3,266.40
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.24	11.64	0.002	3,266.41
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.24	11.64	0.002	3,266.41
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.25	11.65	0.002	3,266.42
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}} + \text{CWED}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.25	11.65	0.002	3,266.42
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}^e$	27	3,348.33	11.72	0.002	3,274.17
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.34	11.74	0.002	3,266.51

Table 3: route occupancy model set

$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,350.91	14.31	0.001	3,272.97
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,350.98	14.37	0.000	3,273.03
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.04	14.44	0.000	3,273.09
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.06	14.45	0.000	3,273.11
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.14	14.53	0.000	3,273.19
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,351.17	14.57	0.000	3,269.34
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.22	14.61	0.000	3,273.27
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}} + \text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,351.24	14.63	0.000	3,269.40
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.25	14.65	0.000	3,273.31
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,351.33	14.73	0.000	3,269.50
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.36	14.75	0.000	3,273.41
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}} + \text{ENN}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,351.36	14.76	0.000	3,269.53
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.41	14.81	0.000	3,273.46
$\psi\{\text{CONTAG}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.41	14.81	0.000	3,273.47
$\psi\{\text{EDGE}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.44	14.84	0.000	3,273.50
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.46	14.86	0.000	3,273.52
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,351.46	14.86	0.000	3,269.63
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.47	14.87	0.000	3,273.52
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.48	14.88	0.000	3,273.54
$\psi\{\text{EDGE}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.52	14.91	0.000	3,273.57
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,351.53	14.93	0.000	3,269.69
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,351.53	14.93	0.000	3,265.70
$\psi\{\text{IJ}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.63	15.03	0.000	3,273.69
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.64	15.04	0.000	3,273.70
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,351.68	15.07	0.000	3,265.84
$\psi\{\text{O:F}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.71	15.11	0.000	3,273.77
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.75	15.15	0.000	3,273.81
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,351.83	15.23	0.000	3,266.00
$\psi\{\text{IJ}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.92	15.32	0.000	3,273.98
$\psi\{\text{IJ}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.94	15.34	0.000	3,273.99
$\psi\{\text{IJ}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,351.97	15.37	0.000	3,274.02
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,352.01	15.41	0.000	3,266.18
$\psi\{\text{IJ}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,352.09	15.49	0.000	3,274.15
$\psi\{\text{IJ}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,352.10	15.50	0.000	3,274.15

Table 3: route occupancy model set

$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,352.17	15.57	0.000	3,270.34
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,352.30	15.70	0.000	3,270.47
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,352.65	16.05	0.000	3,270.82
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}} + \text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,352.69	16.09	0.000	3,270.86
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,352.97	16.36	0.000	3,271.13
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.17	17.56	0.000	3,272.33
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.37	17.77	0.000	3,272.54
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.44	17.84	0.000	3,272.60
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.58	17.98	0.000	3,272.75
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.63	18.02	0.000	3,272.79
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.64	18.04	0.000	3,272.81
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.68	18.08	0.000	3,272.85
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.71	18.10	0.000	3,272.87
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.80	18.20	0.000	3,272.96
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,354.88	18.27	0.000	3,273.04
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,355.06	18.46	0.000	3,273.23
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,355.14	18.54	0.000	3,273.31
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}} + \text{IJI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,355.35	18.75	0.000	3,273.51
$\psi\{\text{STRATA}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,361.03	24.43	0.000	3,271.09

^a Model parameters include route occupancy (ψ), local availability at a survey station given unavailability at the previous station (θ), local availability at a survey station given availability at the previous station (θ'), establishment (γ), abandonment (ε), detection (p), and availability at the unobserved survey station defined by the Markov equilibrium process via θ and θ' (π). Establishment and abandonment parameters were held constant (.) to evaluate the potential influence of land cover covariate(s) on probability of initial route occupancy (ψ) of wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin. Covariates include class-level composition and configuration metrics (McGarigal et al. 2012) for agriculture (ag), deciduous forest (dec), forest cover (forest), grass, upland hardwoods (hard), oak, and open cover (open): area-weighted mean patch size (AREA), clumpiness index (CLUMPY), area-weighted mean Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (ENN), interspersion and juxtaposition index (IJI), largest patch index (LPI), percentage of land cover (PLAND), and mean proximity index (PROX). We also assessed road density (m/ha; ROAD), ratio of open-to-forest cover (O:F), forest cover strata (STRATA; $\leq 20\%$ forest, >20 to $\leq 40\%$ forest, >40 to $\leq 60\%$ forest, >60 to $\leq 80\%$ forest, and $>80\%$ forest), and the following landscape configuration metrics (McGarigal et al. 2012): edge density (EDGE), contrast-weighted edge density (CWED), IJI, and contagion index (CONTAG).

^b Local availability covariates ($\theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}$) from the best-supported model for wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (LPI_{ag} , ENN_{hard} , and IJI_{hard} ; Table 2).

^c Covariates from the best detection probability model ($p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}$) for wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (Survey Period, Time^2 , Wind; Table 1).

- ^d Best-supported model within the route occupancy model set which was further used as the base model in the subsequent model set to evaluate establishment and abandonment of wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (Table 4).
- ^e Best-supported probability of local availability (θ, θ') model for wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (Table 2).

Table 4. Multiseason correlated-replicate model selection results for probability of establishment and abandonment for eastern wild turkeys within 3.2-km buffered (~5,300 ha) gobbling call-count survey routes in southeast Wisconsin, USA, 2016–2018. Models were ranked by the difference (ΔAIC_c) between the model with the lowest Akaike's Information Criterion for small samples (AIC_c) and AIC_c for the current model, K is the number of model parameters, w_i is model weight, and $-2\log(L)$ is the maximized -2 log-likelihood function. Model fit was assessed in Program PRESENCE v12.23 (Hines 2006). Non-converging models are not included within the model set.

Probability of establishment and abandonment model ^a	K	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	w_i	$-2\log(L)$
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}^b, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}^c, \pi\}^{d,e}$	28	3,336.60	0.00	0.926	3,258.66
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,344.91	8.30	0.015	3,263.07
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Other}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,346.46	9.86	0.007	3,264.63
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Other}^2\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,347.56	10.95	0.004	3,261.72
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.63	11.03	0.004	3,265.79
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.85	11.25	0.003	3,266.01
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,347.97	11.37	0.003	3,266.14
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,348.02	11.41	0.003	3,262.18
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.21	11.61	0.003	3,266.38
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.24	11.64	0.003	3,266.40
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Other}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	29	3,348.26	11.65	0.003	3,266.42
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,348.74	12.13	0.002	3,262.90
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,348.92	12.32	0.002	3,263.09
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,349.18	12.58	0.002	3,263.35
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	31	3,349.24	12.64	0.002	3,259.30
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Other}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,349.27	12.66	0.002	3,263.43
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,349.30	12.69	0.002	3,263.46
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,349.36	12.76	0.002	3,263.53
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Other}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,349.40	12.80	0.002	3,263.57
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Other}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,349.67	13.07	0.001	3,263.84
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Other}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Other}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,349.99	13.39	0.001	3,264.16
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,350.30	13.70	0.001	3,264.47
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Other}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,350.41	13.81	0.001	3,264.58
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	31	3,350.75	14.14	0.001	3,260.80
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}^2\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,351.29	14.68	0.001	3,265.45
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Other}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,351.50	14.89	0.001	3,265.66
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\}$	30	3,351.61	15.01	0.001	3,265.78

Table 4: route establishment and abandonment model set

$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,351.69	15.08	0.000	3,265.85
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,351.73	15.12	0.000	3,265.89
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,351.84	15.24	0.000	3,266.01
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,351.85	15.24	0.000	3,266.01
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Other}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,351.85	15.24	0.000	3,266.01
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,351.89	15.29	0.000	3,266.06
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,352.07	15.47	0.000	3,262.13
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,352.10	15.49	0.000	3,266.26
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,352.18	15.58	0.000	3,266.35
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Other}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,352.18	15.58	0.000	3,266.35
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,352.58	15.98	0.000	3,262.64
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,352.75	16.14	0.000	3,262.80
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,353.02	16.42	0.000	3,263.08
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,353.17	16.57	0.000	3,263.23
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,353.29	16.69	0.000	3,263.35
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,353.47	16.87	0.000	3,263.53
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,354.26	17.66	0.000	3,264.32
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,354.97	18.37	0.000	3,256.45
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,355.74	19.13	0.000	3,261.56
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,355.89	19.28	0.000	3,265.94
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,356.11	19.51	0.000	3,266.17
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,356.28	19.67	0.000	3,257.75
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,356.79	20.19	0.000	3,262.62
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,356.93	20.33	0.000	3,258.41
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,357.04	20.44	0.000	3,258.52
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,357.80	21.20	0.000	3,263.63
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,360.01	23.40	0.000	3,261.49
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,360.59	23.99	0.000	3,262.07
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	34	3,361.39	24.79	0.000	3,258.39
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_{\text{se}}\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,362.12	25.52	0.000	3,263.60

^a Model parameters include route occupancy (ψ), local availability at a survey station given unavailability at the previous station (θ), local availability at a survey station given availability at the previous station (θ'), establishment (γ), abandonment (ε), detection (p), and availability at the unobserved survey station defined by the Markov equilibrium process via θ and θ' (π). For southeast Wisconsin, occupancy covariates include proximity index of upland hardwood forest ($\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}$; McGarigal et al. 2012). Establishment and abandonment covariates include number of days with snow cover >30 cm from 1

Table 4: route establishment and abandonment model set

Nov–30 Apr within gobbling call-count survey routes (Snow; NOHRSA 2004), and percentage of row crop agriculture (USDA 2017) planted in corn (Corn), small grains (Grain), or other row crops (Other).

- ^b Local availability covariates (θ, θ' {best_{se}}) from the best-supported model for wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (LPI_{ag} , ENN_{hard} , and IJI_{hard} ; Table 2).
- ^c Detection probability covariates (p {best_{se}}) from the best-supported model for wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (Survey Period, Time², and Wind; Table 1).
- ^d Best-supported probability of route occupancy model for wild turkeys in southeast Wisconsin (Table 3).
- ^e Best-approximating multiseason correlated-replicate occupancy model for wild turkeys southeast Wisconsin. This final model was used to predict the probability of patch-specific occupancy of wild turkeys across the southeast Wisconsin study region.

REFERENCES

- Hines, J. E. (2006). PRESENCE v12.23: Software to estimate patch occupancy and related parameters. U.S. Geological Survey Patuxent Wildlife Research Center. <https://mbr-pwrc.usgs.gov/software/presence.html>. Accessed 7 Nov 2018.
- McGarigal, K., Cushman, S. A., & Ene, E. (2012). FRAGSTATS v4: Spatial pattern analysis program for categorical and contiguous maps. <https://www.umass.edu/landeco/research/fragstats/fragstats.html>. Accessed 25 Jul 2017.
- National Operational Hydrologic Remote Sensing Center (NOHRCS) (2004). Snow Data Assimilation System (SNODAS) data products at National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC), version 1. Boulder, CO: National Snow and Ice Data Center. <https://doi.org/10.7265/N5TB14TC>. Accessed 17 Jun 2018.
- USDA National Agricultural Statistics Service (2017). Wisconsin Cropland Data Layer, 2013–2017. United States Department of Agriculture. Washington D.C. <https://nassgeodata.gmu.edu/CropScape>. Accessed 31 Jan 2018.